

Analysis Plan: Metacognitive Mechanisms of Control over Bodily States

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Version	1.0
Status of current version	prior to access of validation data set (data collection currently ongoing)
Version history:	
-	1.0: 12 May 2025

1 INTRODUCTION

This document contains the analysis plan of the behavioural study of the project entitled “Metacognitive Mechanisms of Control over Bodily States” (METAC). The analysis concerns behavioural, physiological and questionnaire data from a healthy volunteer study conducted at the Translational Neuromodeling Unit (TNU). The study comprises a novel behavioural paradigm, the Respiratory Metacognition of Control Task (RMCT, see section 2), which is motivated by the allostatic self-efficacy theory (ASE; Manjaly et al., 2019; Stephan et al., 2016). This study tests a set of a newly developed computational models of behaviour describing the formation of beliefs regarding control over bodily states. Furthermore, we plan to examine the association of RMCT readouts to questionnaire scores.

The purpose of this analysis plan is to formulate the scientific question(s) and explicitly describe planned analyses.

2 DATA SET

The data set comprises behavioural, physiological and questionnaire data from healthy volunteers. The data is split into a discovery set (20 healthy volunteers) for data exploration and the estimation of empirical priors, and a validation set (containing data of 30-60 healthy volunteers as determined using a Sequential Bayes Factor (SBF) design (Schönbrodt et al., 2017) outlined in section 6) for testing of the main hypotheses. These two data sets remain strictly separated to prevent any information leak.

Figure 1 | Study design of the METAC 1 study. Participants completed a pre-screening and a battery of questionnaires online before coming to the lab. On the experiment day, participants completed the FAS and MFIS questionnaires and the Respiratory Metacognition of Control Task (RMCT) in the lab.

Figure 1 depicts a graphical overview of the design of the METAC 1 study (cross-sectional). Participants were pre-screened for study-relevant information including fatigue scores measured by the Fatigue Assessment Scale (FAS; Michielsen et al., 2003). Upon study inclusion, participants answered demographic/socioeconomic questions and completed the following battery of psychological **questionnaires online** before coming to the lab:

- Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-8; Berth, 2003)
- Trait-related part of the Spielberger State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI-T; Laux, 1981)
- General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSES; Schwarzer, 1993; Schwarzer et al., 1997; Schwarzer and Jerusalem, 1995)
- Multidimensional Assessment of Interoceptive Awareness Version 2 (MAIA-2; Mehling et al., 2018, 2012)
- Perceived Control Items (PCI; Infurna et al., 2011)
- Locus of Control (LOC; Krampen, 1985, 1979)
- Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI; Buysse et al., 1989; Hinz et al., 2017)

On the **experiment day** in the lab, participants completed the Respiratory Metacognition of Control Task (RMCT) and filled in the following two **questionnaires**:

- Fatigue Assessment Scale (FAS; Michielsen et al., 2003)
- Modified Fatigue Impact Scale (MFIS; Zimmermann and Hohlfeld, 1999)

Figure 2 | Task protocol of the RMCT in the METAC 1 study. Overview of the structure of one trial of the RMCT.

Figure 2 displays a graphical summary of the RMCT protocol. The following **behavioural responses** were collected during the task on every trial:

- Jump strength
- Interoceptive prediction \mathbf{y}_{int} (1x80 vector with values in $[0,1]$)
- Presence/absence of inspiratory resistance \mathbf{R} (1x80 vector with binary values $\{0,1\}$)
- Metacognitive judgement of explicit control \mathbf{y}_{mc} (1x80 vector with values in $[0,1]$)

The interoceptive prediction error (PE) can be calculated as $\mathbf{PE} = \mathbf{R} - \mathbf{y}_{int}$. Additionally, the following behavioural responses were collected (after every 10th trial):

- Overall control over breathing \mathbf{y}_c (1x8 vector with values in $[0,1]$)
- Tolerance of inspiratory resistances \mathbf{y}_{tol} (1x8 vector with values in $[0,1]$)

Finally, after completion of the task, we asked participants to rate the aversiveness of the inspiratory loads during the entire paradigm y_{av} (real-valued number in $[0,1]$)

Physiological signals recorded during the RMCT included:

- pressure at the mouth level
- respiratory gas concentrations (O_2 and CO_2)
- air flow
- pulse

3 SCIENTIFIC QUESTIONS

Primary research question

SQ1. Can **perceived control over breathing** be explained as a **function of interoceptive prediction errors** in the RMCT?

Additional questions

SQ2. Is the experience of control during the RMCT related to the overall experience of **fatigue**?

SQ3. Is the experience of control during the RMCT related to **physical, cognitive, and psychosocial** dimensions of **fatigue**?

SQ4. Can the explanation of **fatigue** scores via **sleep and interoception** (Rouault et al., 2023) be improved by taking into account the experience of control during the RMCT?

SQ5. Is the experience of control during the RMCT related to **other constructs of control**?

4 PRE-PROCESSING

The following pre-processing steps are applied to response data \mathbf{y} (collected on a visual-to-analogue scale; VAS) from the RMCT that are coded on the interval $[0,1]$:

- Shrink toward 0.5 by a factor of 0.95 (ensure responses are in the open unit interval)

$$y_{shrink}(k) = 0.95 * (y(k) - 0.5) + 0.5$$

- Apply logit-transformation

$$y_{logit}(k) = \log\left(\frac{y_{shrink}(k)}{1 - y_{shrink}(k)}\right)$$

5 DETAILED DESCRIPTION OF HYPOTHESES & ANALYSES

We provide a detailed description of all our planned analyses and hypothesis tests. Our analyses use a Bayesian approach to statistics and hypothesis tests will be conducted using Bayes Factors (BFs). For the interpretation of the results of our analyses, we will rely on the following scale for the interpretation of Bayes Factors (Kass and Raftery, 1995):

Bayes Factor $BF_{1,0}$	Grades of Evidence	Evidence favours the ...
<0.0067	very strong	Null hypothesis
0.0067 to 0.05	strong	
0.05 to 0.33	positive	
0.33 to 1	barely worth mentioning	
1 to 3	barely worth mentioning	Alternative hypothesis
3 to 20	positive	
20 to 150	strong	
>150	very strong	

Primary hypothesis

- H1. **Perceived control over breathing** can be explained as a function of **interoceptive prediction errors** (PEs) in the RMCT.
- Statistical model: trial-by-trial computational model of behaviour (see Appendix A1 for detailed description of computational cognitive modelling of behaviour)
 - output: \mathbf{y}_{mc}
 - input:
 - presence/absence of inspiratory resistance (\mathbf{R})
 - interoceptive **PE** (transformed to logit space)
 - Statistical threshold: Group Bayes factor $GBF \geq 150$ (Fixed-effects Bayesian Model Selection, FFX BMS) for the comparison between our proposed model (full model \mathbf{M}_{PE+R}) and a control model (null model \mathbf{M}_0); both models are described in the Appendix. This comparison will be used for the SBF design (see section 6).
 - Control for outlier effects: Visualise distribution of log BF's.
 - Additional analysis to assess the (i) relative importance of the different components of \mathbf{M}_{PE+R} and (ii) the prevalence of individual models in the population: RFX BMS on the model space that is specified in the Appendix (Table 1).

Additional hypotheses

The following hypotheses concern the question how (state-like) task-based readouts from the RMCT are related to more stable (trait-like) constructs of fatigue and experienced control that were measured by established questionnaires. Potential variables from the RMCT include estimated posterior mean values (abbreviated by γ , w , *shift*, *scale*, respectively), provided the test of H1 favours model \mathbf{M}_{PE+R} , summary measures of ASE-inspired readouts (average values and variances of overall control and tolerance abbreviated by $\bar{\mathbf{y}}_c$, $\bar{\mathbf{y}}_{tol}$, $Var(\mathbf{y}_c)$, $Var(\mathbf{y}_{tol})$, respectively), and task aversiveness (\mathbf{y}_{av}). For each ANCOVA model in H2-H5, we include only a subset of the previously described predictors. The choice of subset was motivated by exploratory analyses on the discovery set. Specifically, we selected those predictors for whom the odds for inclusion was greater after $\left(\frac{P(incl|D)}{1-P(incl|D)}\right)$ than before seeing the data $\left(\frac{P(incl)}{1-P(incl)}\right)$ (Bergh et al., 2020).

- H2. Model-based estimates of perceived control, other ASE-inspired readouts (overall control, tolerance), and task aversiveness in the RMCT explain overall **fatigue** scores from standard questionnaires (FAS, MFIS).
- Statistical model: Bayesian ANCOVA
 - Dependent variable: MFIS
 - Model $\mathbf{M}_{1,H2}$, linear combination of the following independent variables:
 - γ (if the test of H1 favours model \mathbf{M}_{PE+R})
 - $\bar{\mathbf{y}}_c$
 - $Var(\mathbf{y}_{tol})$
 - \mathbf{y}_{av}
 - Gender
 - Age
 - Intercept
 - Hypothesis test: Bayes factor BF_{10} (comparison of model $\mathbf{M}_{1,H2}$ against reduced model $\mathbf{M}_{0,H2}$ containing only gender, age, and an intercept).
 - Exploratory analysis: Bayes factors for comparing all submodels of $\mathbf{M}_{1,H2}$ against $\mathbf{M}_{0,H2}$
 - Sensitivity analysis for explanation of fatigue scores using a different construct of fatigue: repeat analysis with FAS score as dependent variable

- H3. Model-based estimates of perceived control, other ASE-inspired readouts (overall control, tolerance), and task aversiveness in the RMCT explain **physical, cognitive and psychosocial dimensions of fatigue** (MFIS subscales), respectively.
- Statistical model: Bayesian ANCOVA
 - Dependent variable: MFIS (**cognitive** subscale)
 - Model $M_{1,H3}$, linear combination of the following independent variables:
 - γ (if the test of H1 favours model M_{PE+R})
 - \bar{y}_{tol}
 - $Var(\mathbf{y}_c)$
 - $Var(\mathbf{y}_{tol})$
 - y_{av}
 - Gender
 - Age
 - Intercept
 - Hypothesis test: Bayes factor BF_{10} (comparison of model $M_{1,H3}$ against reduced model $M_{0,H3}$ containing only gender, age, and an intercept).
 - Exploratory analysis: Bayes factors for comparing all submodels of $M_{1,H3}$ against $M_{0,H3}$
 - Repeat analysis for other MFIS subscales (physical, psychosocial) as dependent variables
 - Dependent variable MFIS (**physical** subscale); independent variables: γ and w (if the test of H1 favours model M_{PE+R}), \bar{y}_c , y_{av} , gender, age, and intercept
 - Dependent variable: MFIS (**psychosocial** subscale); independent variables: γ (if the test of H1 favours model M_{PE+R}), \bar{y}_c , $Var(\mathbf{y}_{tol})$, y_{av} , gender, age, and intercept
- H4. Model-based estimates of perceived control, other ASE-inspired readouts (overall control, tolerance), and task aversiveness in the RMCT improve the explanation of **fatigue** scores (FAS, MFIS) based on questionnaire scores (**sleep and interoception**; PSQI and MAIA-2, respectively), as previously used to explain fatigue scores (Rouault et al., 2023).
- Statistical model: Bayesian ANCOVA
 - Dependent variable: MFIS
 - Model $M_{1,H4}$, linear combination of the following independent variables:
 - γ , *scale*, w (if the test of H1 favours model M_{PE+R})
 - \bar{y}_c
 - $Var(\mathbf{y}_{tol})$
 - y_{av}
 - PSQI
 - MAIA-2 (sum of subscales 3 and 8)
 - Gender
 - Age
 - Intercept
 - Hypothesis test: Bayes factor BF_{10} (comparison of model $M_{1,H4}$ against reduced model $M_{0,H4}$ containing only PSQI, MAIA-2 sum of subscales 3 and 8, gender, age, and an intercept).
 - Exploratory analysis: Bayes factors for comparing all submodels of $M_{1,H4}$ against $M_{0,H4}$
 - Sensitivity analysis: repeat with FAS score as dependent variable
- H5. Model-based estimates of perceived control, other ASE-inspired readouts (overall control, tolerance), and task aversiveness in the RMCT explain **constructs of control** from standard questionnaires (GSES, PCI, LOC scales LOC_p (powerful others) and LOC_c (chance)).
- Statistical model: Bayesian ANCOVA
 - Dependent variable: GSES
 - Model $M_{1,H5}$, linear combination of the following independent variables:

- γ (if the test of H1 favours model M_{PE+R})
- $Var(\mathbf{y}_c)$
- Gender
- Age
- Intercept
- Hypothesis test: Bayes factor BF_{10} (comparison of model $M_{1,H5}$ against reduced model $M_{0,H5}$ containing only gender, age, and an intercept).
- Exploratory analysis: Bayes factors for comparing all submodels of $M_{1,H5}$ against $M_{0,H5}$
- Repeat analysis for
 - Dependent variable: PCI, independent variables: $\gamma, shift$ (if the test of H1 favours model M_{PE+R}), gender, age, and intercept
 - Dependent variable: LOC_p; independent variables: γ, w (if the test of H1 favours model M_{PE+R}), $Var(\mathbf{y}_{tol})$, y_{av} , gender, age, and intercept
 - Dependent variable: LOC_c; independent variables: γ (if the test of H1 favours model M_{PE+R}), y_{av} , gender, age, and intercept

6 SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION OF VALIDATION SET (SBF DESIGN)

Sample size of the validation set will be determined using a Sequential Bayes Factor (SBF) design, an established procedure for sequential hypothesis testing in the Bayesian domain which is commonly recommended for pre-registered reports by neuroscientific journals (Chambers and Tzavella, 2021; Schönbrodt et al., 2017). Figure 3 displays a flowchart of the SBF design in the METAC 1 study. The criterion that needs to be fulfilled to terminate data acquisition is the Group Bayes Factors (GBF) computed in H1 ($GBF \geq 150$). The first test will be conducted at a sample size of $N_{\min}=30$ for the validation set. If the criterion is not met, data collection continues in steps of 10 until either the criterion is fulfilled or the validation set reaches a size of $N_{\max}=60$.

Figure 3 | Flowchart of the SBF design used for sample size determination of the validation set in the METAC 1 study.

REFERENCES

- Bergh, D. van den, Doorn, J. van, Marsman, M., Draws, T., Kesteren, E.-J. van, Derks, K., Dablander, F., Gronau, Q.F., Kucharský, Š., Gupta, A.R.K.N., Sarafoglou, A., Voelkel, J.G., Stefan, A., Ly, A., Hinne, M., Matzke, D., Wagenmakers, E.-J., 2020. A Tutorial on Conducting and Interpreting a Bayesian ANOVA in JASP. *L'Année psychologique* 120, 73–96. <https://doi.org/10.3917/anpsy1.201.0073>
- Berth, H., 2003. B. Löwe, R.L. Spitzer, S. Zipfel & W. Herzog: PHQ-D. gesundheitsfragebogen für patienten. 12, 90–93.
- Buysse, D.J., Reynolds, C.F., Monk, T.H., Berman, S.R., Kupfer, D.J., 1989. The Pittsburgh sleep quality index: A new instrument for psychiatric practice and research. *Psychiatry Research* 28, 193–213. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1781\(89\)90047-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-1781(89)90047-4)
- Chambers, C.D., Tzavella, L., 2021. The past, present and future of Registered Reports. *Nature Human Behaviour* 2021 6:1 6, 29–42. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-021-01193-7>
- Harrison, O.K., Köchli, L., Marino, S., Luechinger, R., Hennel, F., Brand, K., Hess, A.J., Frässle, S., Iglesias, S., Vinckier, F., Petzschnner, F.H., Harrison, S.J., Stephan, K.E., 2021. Interoception of breathing and its relationship with anxiety. *Neuron* 0, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2021.09.045>
- Hess, A.J., Iglesias, S., Köchli, L., Marino, S., Müller-Schrader, M., Rigoux, L., Mathys, C., Harrison, O.K., Heinzle, J., Frässle, S., Stephan, K.E., 2024. Bayesian Workflow for Generative Modeling in Computational Psychiatry. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.02.19.581001>
- Hinz, A., Glaesmer, H., Brähler, E., Löffler, M., Engel, C., Enzenbach, C., Hegerl, U., Sander, C., 2017. Sleep quality in the general population: psychometric properties of the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index, derived from a German community sample of 9284 people. *Sleep Medicine* 30, 57–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sleep.2016.03.008>
- Infurna, F.J., Gerstorf, D., Ram, N., Schupp, J., Wagner, G.G., 2011. Long-Term Antecedents and Outcomes of Perceived Control. *Psychology and Aging* 26, 559. <https://doi.org/10.1037/A0022890>
- Kass, R.E., Raftery, A.E., 1995. Bayes factors. *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 90, 773–795. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1995.10476572>
- Krampen, G., 1985. Zur Bedeutung von Kontrollüberzeugungen in der klinischen Psychologie. *Zeitschrift für Klinische Psychologie* 14.
- Krampen, G., 1979. Differenzierungen des Konstruktes der Kontrollüberzeugung. *Deutsche Bearbeitung und Anwendung der IPC-Skalen. Zeitschrift für experimentelle und angewandte Psychologie* 26.
- Laux, L., 1981. *Das State-Trait-Angstinventar (STAI) : theoretische Grundlagen und Handanweisung.* Beltz, Weinheim.
- Manjaly, Z.M., Harrison, N.A., Critchley, H.D., Do, C.T., Stefanics, G., Wenderoth, N., Lutterotti, A., Müller, A., Stephan, K.E., 2019. Pathophysiological and cognitive mechanisms of fatigue in multiple sclerosis. *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery and Psychiatry* 90, 642–651. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jnnp-2018-320050>
- Mehling, W.E., Acree, M., Stewart, A., Silas, J., Jones, A., 2018. The Multidimensional Assessment of Interoceptive Awareness, Version 2 (MAIA-2). *PLOS ONE* 13, e0208034. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0208034>
- Mehling, W.E., Price, C., Daubenmier, J.J., Acree, M., Bartmess, E., Stewart, A., 2012. The Multidimensional Assessment of Interoceptive Awareness (MAIA). *PLOS ONE* 7, e48230. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0048230>
- Michielsen, H.J., De Vries, J., Van Heck, G.L., 2003. Psychometric qualities of a brief self-rated fatigue measure: The Fatigue Assessment Scale. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research* 54, 345–352. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3999\(02\)00392-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3999(02)00392-6)
- Rouault, M., Pereira, I., Galioulline, H., Fleming, S.M., Stephan, K.E., Manjaly, Z.-M., 2023. Interoceptive and metacognitive facets of fatigue in multiple sclerosis. *European Journal of Neuroscience* 58, 2603–2622. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejn.16048>

- Schöbi, D., Homberg, F., Frässle, S., Endepols, H., Moran, R.J., Friston, K.J., Tittgemeyer, M., Heinzle, J., Stephan, K.E., 2021. Model-based prediction of muscarinic receptor function from auditory mismatch negativity responses. *NeuroImage* 237, 118096. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NEUROIMAGE.2021.118096>
- Schönbrodt, F.D., Wagenmakers, E.J., Zehetleitner, M., Perugini, M., 2017. Sequential hypothesis testing with Bayes factors: Efficiently testing mean differences. *Psychological Methods* 22, 322–339. <https://doi.org/10.1037/met0000061>
- Schwarzer, R., 1993. Measurement of perceived self-efficacy. *Forschung an der Freien*.
- Schwarzer, R., Bäßler, J., Kwiatek, P., Schröder, K., Zhang, J.X., 1997. The assessment of optimistic self-beliefs: comparison of the German, Spanish, and Chinese versions of the general self-efficacy scale. *Applied Psychology* 46, 69–88.
- Schwarzer, R., Jerusalem, M., 1995. Generalized self-efficacy scale. J. Weinman, S. Wright, & M. Johnston, *Measures in health psychology: A user's portfolio. Causal and control beliefs* 35, 37.
- Stephan, K.E., Manjaly, Z.M., Mathys, C.D., Weber, L.A.E., Paliwal, S., Gard, T., Tittgemeyer, M., Fleming, S.M., Haker, H., Seth, A.K., Petzschner, F.H., 2016. Allostatic self-efficacy: A metacognitive theory of dyshomeostasis-induced fatigue and depression. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience* 10, 550. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2016.00550>
- Zimmermann, C., Hohlfeld, R., 1999. „Fatigue“ bei multipler Sklerose. *Nervenarzt* 70, 566–574. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s001150050482>

APPENDIX

A1 Computational Cognitive Modelling of Behaviour

In H1, we propose that the experience of control over respiration is a function of interoceptive PEs. We formalise this hypothesis in the form of a generative model for trial-by-trial reports of perceived control over breathing. It takes the form of an (autoregressive) AR(1) model:

$$z(k) = \alpha + \beta_1 PE(k) + \beta_2 R(k) + \gamma z(k-1) \quad (1)$$

where z represents the participant's perceived control on each trial k in logit space. α is a constant offset, β_1 is a weighting factor for the influence of the interoceptive PE (in logit space) at trial k , β_2 weighs the influence of the presence/absence of an inspiratory resistance R at trial k . γ represents the dependence on past experience of control from the previous trial $k-1$. Equation 1 can be rewritten in an explicit fashion by solving the recursive formula and subsequent reformulation of parameters:

$$z(k) = \alpha \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \gamma^j + \beta_1 \sum_{j=1}^k \gamma^{k-j} PE(j) + \beta_2 \sum_{j=1}^k \gamma^{k-j} R(j) + \gamma^k z_0 \quad (2)$$

$$= \alpha \frac{1-\gamma^k}{1-\gamma} + \beta_1 \sum_{j=1}^k \gamma^{k-j} PE(j) + \beta_2 \sum_{j=1}^k \gamma^{k-j} R(j) + \gamma^k z_0 \quad (3)$$

where z_0 is the initial value of perceived control at trial 0. Under the substitution

$$\alpha, \beta_1, \beta_2, z_0 \rightarrow \hat{\alpha} * scale, scale, scale * w, \hat{z}_0 * scale \quad (4)$$

we can rewrite the equation as follows:

$$z(k) = scale \cdot \left(\hat{\alpha} \frac{1-\gamma^k}{1-\gamma} + \sum_{j=1}^k \gamma^{k-j} PE(j) + w \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \gamma^{k-j} R(j) \right) + \gamma^k \hat{z}_0 \right) \quad (5)$$

Using the substitution

$$\hat{\alpha} \frac{1}{1-\gamma}, \hat{z}_0 - \hat{\alpha} \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \rightarrow shift, \tilde{z}_0 \quad (6)$$

we arrive at the following equation:

$$z(k) = scale \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \gamma^{k-j} PE(j) + w \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \gamma^{k-j} R(j) \right) + \gamma^k \tilde{z}_0 + shift \right) \quad (7)$$

The parameters in the reformulated model (Eq. 7) can be interpreted as follows: γ represents the dependence of the current experience of control on past experience of control. The latter, in turn, depends on past values of PE, R, and \tilde{z}_0 . For this reason, γ in Eq. 7 denotes the influence of multiple factors from the past over different timescales. w defines the influence of the history of inspiratory resistances R obtained during the task. $scale$ represents the sensitivity towards differences in PE and R, and $shift$ represents the tendency towards experiencing high or low control.

Under the assumption that observations $\mathbf{y}_{mc,logit}$ follow a normal distribution, the likelihood function of the generative model is defined as follows:

$$p(\mathbf{y}_{mc,logit}) = N(\mathbf{z}, \Sigma_{mc}) \quad (8)$$

To get a full generative model, we need to define a prior probability distribution over the parameter space $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\gamma, w, \tilde{z}_0, scale, shift, \Sigma_{mc})$. We assume that the prior distribution factorises into marginal priors

$$p(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = p\left(\log\left(\frac{\gamma + 1}{2 - (\gamma + 1)}\right)\right)p(w)p(\tilde{z}_0)p(scale)p(shift)p(\log(\Sigma_{mc})) \quad (9)$$

where each marginal prior corresponds to a normal distribution. Sufficient statistics of the marginal *initial priors* are listed in Table 2. These initial priors are used for inverting the generative model of the discovery data set (N=20), resulting in estimates of the mean and variance of the approximate marginal posteriors. These will then be used as the sufficient statistics of our *empirical priors* which will be used for analysis of the validation data set. This established two-step procedure enables the use of informative priors covering a plausible range of behaviour while avoiding the problem of double-dipping (Harrison et al., 2021; Hess et al., 2024; Schöbi et al., 2021).

We will compare a full model (\mathbf{M}_{PE+R} in Table 1), which includes both PE and R as predictor variables from Eq. 7, to reduced versions containing only one of the two predictors (\mathbf{M}_R : R; \mathbf{M}_{PE} : PE) and a null model (\mathbf{M}_0) which assumes perceived control to be constant over time but allows for subject-specific levels of perceived control. Table 1 lists the predicted experience of control for all four models in our model space:

Table 1 | Predicted experience of control \mathbf{z} for all four models in the model space.

Model	Perceived control \mathbf{z}
\mathbf{M}_0	$z(k) = shift$
\mathbf{M}_R	$z(k) = scale \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \gamma^{k-j} R(j) + \gamma^k \tilde{z}_0 + shift \right)$
\mathbf{M}_{PE}	$z(k) = scale \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \gamma^{k-j} PE(j) + \gamma^k \tilde{z}_0 + shift \right)$
\mathbf{M}_{PE+R}	$z(k) = scale \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^k \gamma^{k-j} PE(j) + w \left(\gamma^{k-j} R(j) \right) + \gamma^k \tilde{z}_0 + shift \right)$

Table 2 | Sufficient statistics of the marginal *initial prior* distributions. All parameters have Gaussian marginal priors. *Initial prior* means (\mathbf{pE}) and variances (\mathbf{pC}) are both listed for each model (rows) and parameter corresponding to the different models (columns).

		parameters					
		$\log\left(\frac{(\gamma + 1)}{2 - (\gamma + 1)}\right)$	<i>shift</i>	<i>scale</i>	\check{z}_0	<i>w</i>	$\log(\Sigma)$
M_0	\mathbf{pE}_0	-	0	-	-	-	$\log(2)$
	\mathbf{pC}_0	-	4	-	-	-	1
M_R	\mathbf{pE}_R	0	0	0	-0.04	-	$\log(2)$
	\mathbf{pC}_R	4	4	4	0	-	1
M_{PE}	\mathbf{pE}_{PE}	0	0	0	-0.04	-	$\log(2)$
	\mathbf{pC}_{PE}	4	4	4	0	-	1
M_{PE+R}	\mathbf{pE}_{PE+R}	0	0	0	-0.04	0	$\log(2)$
	\mathbf{pC}_{PE+R}	4	4	4	0	4	1